

Codeless teaching of robot-arm positioning in VR

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Abstract. Industry workers must teach new skills to robots for common manufacturing processes that change frequently. They must be able to do so without writing code and without stopping robots that are in operation, to get them reprogrammed. Vocational students must be able to learn and practice these robot-teaching skills with different robot even when institutions can offer limited exposure to robots to practice with. Virtual reality allows interacting naturally with the hologram of a robot's digital twin, using spoken language and by hand-guiding it in the workspace. This paper presents virtual reality natural interactions with the hologram of the digital twin of a robot to teach it routines for approaching a region of interest in the workspace. The user can also teach the robot to position itself with precision on a point, by using machine vision on robot captured images from the virtual scene. A user study provides an initial validation of key design decisions and first implementation.

Keywords: Robot teaching, natural interaction, virtual reality.

1 Introduction

This paper presents the development of a virtual reality (VR) solution to facilitate the programming of a routine that is frequently encountered in production: the approach of the robot's end effector to a region of interest and its precise positioning on a selected point of interest. The aim is to meet the requirements of industry workers (frequent reprogramming of robots without halting ongoing production). Also, requirements of vocational school candidates to becoming industry workers, who have very limited access to hands on work with robots in their institutions.

Industry workers need agile ways to reprogram robots frequently, in response to market demands for increasingly high levels of production personalization. Since production workers are not robot programmers, they cannot be expected to write or edit code in robots' programs. Instead, they must be able to teach skills to robots through natural (i.e., unlearned) communication channels, such as hand guided movement and spoken language.

For workers to teach rather than program robots, programming by demonstration techniques have been proposed in the literature [1]. Several collaborative robots in the market offer kinesthetic programming by demonstration (kPbD) functionalities to learn

from a human moving their end effector across the workspace, sometimes with the additional aid of machine vision. However, from a productivity point of view, a major limitation of these techniques is that robots must remain offline (i.e., not in production) while they are being taught.

With the solution proposed here, a worker can teach a robot in VR by interacting with the holographic version of the digital twin of the physical robot, as they would do in the physical environment.

The rest of this paper first provides a description of the design and implementation of the system. Then, the report of a system evaluation user study is provided.

2 Design and implementation

With these requirements, VR tools were developed for a user (industry worker) to teach a robot approach and precise positioning routines. The extended reality (XR) scene was developed using Unity, to be deployed on the MASTER open XR platform, which is built upon the VIROO[®] platform¹ [2].

Fig. 1. Left: System architecture.

Figure 1 shows the system architecture. The VIROO server contains the XR scene that users retrieve for interacting. This may be a virtual (VR, as in this implementation) or a mixed reality (MR) scene. The scene is loaded in the user's local workstation, and it maintains updated status with the VIROO server to support multiplayer execution. The ROS (Robot Operating System) block interfaces the XR scene with the robot, either holographic (digital twin of the physical robot) or physical. It provides trajectories calculation and interfaces with machine-vision tools. It generates a robot program according to the interactions in the scene. The use of this block in the architecture assures that any ROS-based robot can be configured easily to use the XR tools for robot programming described here. The Unity scene is connected to ROS through a TCP connection among both endpoints. Through this pipeline it was possible to subscribe and publish to ROS topics and create or call services and actions from Unity to ROS and vice versa.

The diagram also shows integration with a *voice dialogue system module* (to enable spoken communication with the robot) and integration with a *machine vision module* (to analyze images of the region of interest captured by the on-board camera of the robot). The dialogue system is an adaptation of KIDE41 [3]. This is a generic, modular

¹ <https://www.virtualwareco.com/viroo/>

framework that allows implementing task-oriented dialogue capabilities in industrial contexts, using semantic technologies as its core. The key element extraction and *polarity interpreter* modules of the system were implemented using Large Language Models (LLMs) for enhanced versatility. As for the integration with machine vision tools, a Halcon² procedure has been developed, based on its computer vision libraries.

3 Interactive robot teaching

The immersive VR scene developed represents a workbench in an industrial environment (Fig. 2). On the workbench there is a robot arm (KUKA LBR iiwa 14 R820), next to a region of interest: a square plate containing parts (nuts and washers).

Fig. 2. In orange, hologram of the digital twin of the robot being taught. The green hologram is a moving preview of the trajectory calculated for the robot to reach a target pose. The red sphere with an arrow is a proxy for the 6DOFs target pose of the robot’s end effector. Left: Target pose over region of interest. Right: Target pose precisely defined on a point of interest.

Communication of the user with the robot was mediated by a virtual agent that understood the user’s voice requests and turned them into actions for the robot system to execute. In turn, it also communicated with the user through two channels: synthetic voice and holographic displays in the scene (Fig. 3), where written text and images (e.g., results of machine vision analyses) were displayed.

3.1 Teaching the robot to approach the region of interest

A kPbD technique was implemented to teach the robot new routines for approaching a region of interest. Similar to the technique in [4], the user indicated the desired final pose for the end effector of the robot. They did this by dragging, turning and dropping in the workspace above the region of interest a dedicated hologram (a red sphere with an arrow that emerged radially from it), proxy for the robot’s end effector (Fig. 2, left). The 6-DOF pose of the proxy hologram (its location and orientation in space) indicated the desired pose for the robot’s end effector. The tool queried with ROS the existence of a trajectory for the end effector to reach that pose. If found, a preview animation of

² <https://www.mvtec.com/products/halcon>

the robot arm moving to that pose was shown in a loop. If the user decided it was an adequate trajectory, they asked the robot to execute it, resulting in the actual movement of the primary hologram.

Fig. 3. Left: display of image captured by robot and annotated by machine vision module. Right: display of written transcription of the request made verbally by the user.

3.2 Teaching the robot to position itself precisely on a point of interest

Once above the region of interest, the goal was to position with precision the robot's end effector on a point of interest selected by the user from the region of interest: a specific vertex of a selected nut, or a specific center of a selected nut or washer. Since the technique of dragging a proxy hologram (used for approach movement) was limited in the precision it could deliver, aid from machine vision was needed.

After a spoken request of the user, the robot captured an image of the region of interest with its on-board camera (virtual camera with the same properties as the real camera IDS UI-5240CP). The image was analyzed with the external machine vision module. The image captured in VR was synthetic, but the vision algorithms treated it like any real image. The vision software extracted the desired features from the image (i.e., vertices and centers), and returned an annotated version of the same image with elements and interest points outlined and labelled with numbers (Fig. 3, left). The user selected an object and specific point on it and asked the robot to move to it. With this information, the system computed the target pose for the end effector on the point of interest, with the precision offered by camera and machine vision SW (Fig. 2, right).

The speech requests were made in two stages, and they could be formulated with freedom of choice of words and sentence structure. The first request was to find instances of a specific type of part (nut or washer) and feature (center of vertex) in it. Second, to move to a selected numbered object from among those returned by the analysis (e.g., nut number two), on a specific point (e.g., vertex number five).

4 Evaluation in user study

10 users (4 female) opted to participate in a user study aimed at evaluating the design and development of the robot programming tool. Participants rated in a 10-point scale their familiarity with industrial environments ($M=7.7$; $SD=0.64$), with industrial robots

($M=7.4$; $SD=0.1.5$) and with XR applications ($M=6$; $SD=2.61$). All participants were educated to university degree level.

The study took place in the virtual scene described in the sections above. The experimental task involved programming two actions for the robot. First, to approach its end effector to the region of interest, which contained nuts and washers in unsorted fashion. Then, to position its end effector precisely above a specific point of interest that they selected, by dialoguing with the system in two stages, as described in section 3.2. Participants completed 3 programming tasks (see list below), presented in random order. All participants completed the three tasks.

- Move the robot to the center of a selected nut.
- Move the robot to a chosen vertex of a selected nut.
- Move the robot to the center of a selected washer.

After the execution of each of the 3 robot programming tasks, participants responded to two quick questions (based on the SEQ questionnaire), rating ease of the programming task and satisfaction with the result obtained. They also filled out a raw NASA-TLX questionnaire, to pinpoint the main source of performance problems [5]. Complemented by user comments, some frustration was reported at occasionally having to repeat voice requests until well understood, which added to time pressure to complete tasks. Error bars in all graphs reported represent 95% confidence intervals.

Fig. 4. Questionnaires after each task repetition. Left: ease of the task and satisfaction with the result. Right: Subjective task load components and Task-Load Index (NASA-TLX).

After the study, participants responded to questionnaires (Fig. 5, left and right) assessing key design features: graphics, interactions, means for moving in the scene, language used and validity of the tool to train persons in codeless robot teaching. While consistently high, room for improvement was identified in the speech input channel becoming a better understander of user spoken requests, according to users.

Fig. 5. Post-study questionnaires to assess design, in 5-point (left) and 11-point (right) scales.

After the study, participants were asked to compare the MASTER training solution vs. traditional forms of training, in two categories: perceived safety during training and ease of use for training. While in the study users only interacted with the MASTER training solution, it was explained that traditional training would have involved classroom training combined with hands on practice with a physical robot.

Fig. 6. Post-study comparison between the MASTER training and traditional forms of training.

5 Conclusion and acknowledgement

Results indicate that the tools were considered easy to use and effective for teaching robots (Fig. 4), even more than traditional learning techniques (Fig. 6). Key design decisions were rated highly (Fig. 5), but the speech input channel needs improvement to understand users' spoken requests more reliably. Still, speaking naturally to the robot was identified as a main asset of this solution by several participants. Future work will support other common industrial robot tasks, with improved interaction.

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